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Demonstrating large pit thermal energy storages and improving their components, processes, and procedures for an accelerated realisation of 100% sustainable district heating networks in Europe.

INPUT DATA REQUIRED AND SOURCES FOR SIMULATION STUDIES ON LTES INTEGRATION IN DH SYSTEMS

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Terms, definitions and abbreviated terms

CAPEX	Capital expenditures
DH	District heating
DHN	District heating network
ETS	Emission trading system
GA	Grant agreement
GIS	Geo information system
HDD	Heating degree day(s)
IEA	International energy agency
LTES	Large thermal energy storage
OPEX	Operational expenditures
PTES	Pit thermal energy storage
TCP	Technology collaboration platform
TES	Thermal energy storage

1. Introduction

At the early phase of a project on the integration of a large thermal energy storage (LTES) into a district heating system, it is necessary to evaluate the added value of different solutions. The process typically starts with gathering data to understand the current situation (Status Quo) and evaluate possible solutions towards the own economic and environmental project goals. Based on the gathered information, their analysis and project goals, different promising energy system concepts can be proposed. Next step is to carry out an assessment from a technical and economic point of view, to roughly size the different concepts as well as to do a comparison between them and with the reference case. Due to the inherent dynamics of thermal energy storage system, it is a common practice to support the system evaluation step with of simulation studies. These simulations help to model and account for these dynamic behaviours, providing a clearer understanding of system performance, facilitating the rough sizing of the main components and providing the basic data for the evaluation of the system and thus serve as a basis for the decision-making process.

The data acquisition process for the early project phase related to the Analysis of the Status Quo, definition of integration concepts of LTES, and realization of simulation studies, is a necessary step and often a resource intensive task. Based on the importance of this task and aware of the project-consortium experience, it is decided to provide a comprehensive overview of the data required for modelling and simulation. Furthermore, the document includes potential sources for most of the listed datasets as well as a hint on the relevance of the specific dataset, e.g. indicating at which stage of the project this dataset should be available and for what reason.

The document is divided into two main parts. Section 2 provides an overview of commonly used and relevant data required to carry out simulation studies and analysis on the integration of LTES in a DH system, while section 3 focuses on a subset of the listed data, especially the data that is usually not provided by the DH operator and need to be gathered from other sources or estimated with help of simple methods and/or well-founded assumptions.

2. Overview of input data

A first overview of data required, classified by potential data-source for simulation studies, has been prepared by the consortium and is summarized below. Notice, that in case of a new DH system, there is no DH operator to gather information from. In that case, the listed information needs to be gathered from third party sources or be estimated.

TABLE 1: LIST OF DATASETS THAT ARE USUALLY PROVIDED BY DH OPERATORS.

Datasets usually provided by DH operators
Load profile of the overall DH system broken down by the available production units (mainly heating power and temperatures with an hourly data resolution for one year).
Information about the main heating units (energy carrier, max power, heat efficiency or cogeneration efficiencies).
Specifications of existing ¹ piping network (e.g. nominal diameter, flowrates) as basis for definition of reasonable volume flow rates and identification of potential bottlenecks.
Heat source of the thermal energy storage (key for the energy system concept definition and relevant to determine the cost -if any - of the heat being charged)
<p>Thermal energy storage charge and discharge profile for the whole year (in power or as volume/mass flow rate and corresponding LTES inlet temperatures).</p> <p>In regards of the profile for the charge-discharge of the TES...</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Either a specific profile is directly provided (somehow a clear schedule on when energy is available and needed for and from the TES system is known), • or the required information to derive such profile needs to be provided. This primarily includes the maximum charging and discharging capacities (these are provided as a requirement or are considered a variable on the definition of the charge-discharge profile, i.e. are part of the optimization process in which capacities and CAPEX are considered) and necessary information to define a proper control strategy. Developing such a strategy requires additional data and a thorough understanding of the system. The specific information needed depends on the complexity of the control strategy. For simpler strategies, it may only require details about heat production units that generate surplus heat (e.g., waste heat) for charging the TES, and the target heat production units to be substituted (e.g., gas boilers) for identifying optimal discharge times. More advanced strategies may incorporate factors such as OPEX (e.g. electricity prices and fuel costs), and technical parameters (e.g. efficiencies of heat production units). <p>In addition to charge-discharge profiles, temperature information is important: heat source temperatures matter during charging, and the supply temperature set point for the DH system is crucial during discharging.</p>
Heat price ² (revenue). Especially relevant on evaluation of energy system concepts where the addition of new consumers is considered.

¹ For a new DH network or extension of the DH network this can be an outcome of the investigations.

² Heat price might be in near future accessible via third party sources, i.e. to be moved to Table 2. E.g. in Austria the platform www.waermepreise.at is available to increase price transparency in the heating and cooling sector by presenting tariff structures for heating and cooling to consumers.

TABLE 2: LIST OF DATASETS THAT CAN BE PROVIDED BY EITHER DH OPERATORS OR THIRD-PARTY SOURCES.

Datasets that can be either provided by DH operator or a third-party source
Weather data (mainly outdoor air temperatures and solar radiation values, especially if a solar thermal, photovoltaic or hybrid collector installation(s) is present in the system)
Land available
Energy market prices (historical and forecasted data): Relevant spot markets for energy carriers considered, e.g. oil, gas, electricity, coal, and/or biomass
If applicable, regulated network tariffs
General unit cost and environmental data: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CO₂ Taxes, CO₂ emission factors of electricity • CO₂ ETS prices • Cost of land • CAPEX and OPEX (e.g. cost of fuels and electricity) of the different heating technologies • Tariffs applied to revenues from technologies such as combined heat and power plants

TABLE 3: LIST OF DATASETS THAT ARE USUALLY PROVIDED BY THIRD PARTY SOURCES.

Datasets usually gathered from third party sources
Presence of groundwater / Water level ³
Soil properties

Notice that some of the above data such as DHN temperatures, flow rates, etc. are site-specific and can be only supplied by the DHN operator. However, in some cases site-specific data are not known by the DHN operator but can alternatively be obtained from third party sources (e.g. weather data services). The next section focuses on the latter category of data.

3. Description of input data

The present section includes a more detailed description of the different datasets required for the simulation studies with special attention to the datasets that are gathered from third party sources and/or addressed with help of well-founded assumptions.

For each dataset, the following information is included,

- **Relevance:** This section highlights the purpose of the dataset's information, emphasizing its importance and indicating the project phase in which the information is needed.
- **Sources:** It contains a list of potential sources for the given dataset, mainly classified as “free to use” and “cost-based”. A short description is added including a few details and (if available) experiences of the consortium with the given data source.

³ Data gathered or determined with a geological study.

3.1 Weather data

Relevance

Weather data, especially outdoor air temperatures, have a strong influence on the DH and TES system and are therefore very relevant regarding,

- Heat load profile is closely linked to outdoor air temperature, particularly when temperatures fall below a certain threshold (depending on different factors, e.g. building envelope) where heat demand primarily serves space heating and secondly serves domestic hot water.
- Setpoint temperature. Most DH operators operate their system with a variable supply temperature as a function of the outdoor air temperature. As a result, return temperature tends to also depend on temperature.
- Heat losses of thermal energy storages. The heat losses of TES are proportional to the temperature difference with the surroundings (air and soil).
- Efficiency of different heating technologies. Performance of different technologies such as air source heat pumps and thermal solar installations are affected by the outdoor air temperature.

Notice that in the context of the TREASURE project, the historical data of heat load profile and/or set point temperatures will already account for the effect of the outdoor air temperature on them, while TES heat losses, storage efficiencies etc. refer mainly to the energy system concept under study and are therefore outputs of simulation studies.

Furthermore, solar irradiation data is clearly relevant for solar technologies such as photovoltaic, solar thermal and hybrid collectors. The solar irradiation and sky temperature also influence the top loss and surface temperatures of TES and surrounding soil. This effect can be accounted for by some simulation models.

Notice that the influence of weather data on the above listed factors (e.g. heat losses, ...) and datasets (e.g. heat load profile), induces an indirect relation between all these factors. To ensure reliable results, consistency of the datasets is required. To illustrate this issue, consider the case where the heat load profile and solar thermal heat production are based on different weather datasets. In this case discrepancies can arise that yield an over- or underestimation of the solar fraction which leads to a wrong design due to incorrect estimations, and ultimately to an underperforming or unsuitable system.

Sources

Free to use sources:

- Databases at European level. E.g. Photovoltaic Geographical Information System (PVGIS)⁴. PVGIS strongly focuses on estimation of photovoltaic system energy productions. However, it also allows to export weather data (e.g. dry bulb temperature, global horizontal irradiation, ...) for a typical meteorological year (TRY) based on the most “typical” month for a set of years (e.g. from 2005 to 2020 for PVGIS-SARAH2 dataset),
- Tool-focused weather databases e.g. EnergyPlus⁵ and energyPRO⁶. In the case of EnergyPlus mostly typical weather file from different sources (e.g. International Weather for Energy Calculations IWECC) are available. It is worth mentioning that export functions are targeted at their own application, i.e. “.epw” format is available for download. If the simulation tool is not able to directly use this file format, a conversion step will be necessary.
- National meteorological and geophysical service of Austria (Geosphere Austria)⁷. Geosphere Austria has a network of more than 250 meteorological stations Austria-wide and has recently (years 2021 and 2022) open sourced its data. It provides different services such as access to historical data (e.g. daily, hourly or 10-minute data) or weather forecast (e.g. 15-minute resolution for a 3-hour time horizon). The services can be directly consulted in their Data Hub⁸.
- Further national meteorological services such as Deutscher Wetterdienst (DWD)⁹ in Germany, National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL)¹⁰ of the USA or Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut¹¹ in Denmark.
- Independent sources based on volunteer work such as Climate.OneBuilding.org¹². Weather files for different regions through the world (Europe, Africa, ...) are available in different formats (e.g. .epw, .clm, ...).

⁴ PHOTOVOLTAIC GEOGRAPHICAL INFORMATION SYSTEM. Joint Research Centre.
<https://re.jrc.ec.europa.eu/>

⁵ Weather Data. EnergyPlus. <https://energyplus.net/weather>

⁶ Getting climate data from energyPRO online server. EMD International A/S. <https://www.emd-international.com/files/energypro/HowToGuides/Getting%20climate%20data%20from%20energyPRO%20online%20server.pdf>. November 2013.

⁷ GeoSphere Austria – Bundesanstalt für Geologie, Geophysik, Klimatologie und Meteorologie.
<https://www.geosphere.at>

⁸ Data Hub der GeoSphere Austria. <https://data.hub.geosphere.at/>

⁹ Deutscher Wetterdienst. <https://www.dwd.de/>

¹⁰ National Solar Radiation Database (NSRDB). National Renewable Energy Laboratory.
<https://nsrdb.nrel.gov/data-viewer>

¹¹ Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut. <https://www.dmi.dk/>

¹² Lawrie, Linda K, Drury B Crawley. 2022. Development of Global Typical Meteorological Years (TMYx).
<http://climate.onebuilding.org>

- Tools such as AixWeather¹³ that facilitates the generation of weather data in suitable formats for different simulation software (e.g. EnergyPlus) using different sources (e.g. historical data from DWD).

Cost-based sources:

- Weather specialized software such as Meteonorm¹⁴. Meteonorm is a common data source used in the modelling and simulation context. It provides weather data (historical data and future climate scenarios) in an hourly resolution. It has great features such as weather data interpolation to provide location specific data as well as great flexibility in terms of export functions. Advancements are done to modernize Meteonorm, e.g. in May 2025 a new API¹⁵ release was launched.

3.2 Land available

Relevance

A first step which should happen early in the project is to identify the potential sites available for the implementation and the potential obstacles for each.

The first interest of those investigations which can be noted, is the fact that the site selection can reveal limitations regarding the available area and thus the volume of the PTES. For example, if the pre-feasibility study concluded to an optimal PTES volume of 500.000 m³, but the land available is only one hectare, this volume cannot be reached in practice (the TES could be divided into several smaller TES, but this will usually lead to a more complex and costlier project). Thus, this information (e.g. land classification, price of land, legal requirements, zoning restrictions, and environmental impact assessments, etc.) should be gathered as early as possible to evaluate the actual potential of the project. Furthermore, the different requirements (e.g. location in water protection areas) will influence the permitting process and may also impact the project planning and timelines.

Moreover, the site identification is a prerequisite for further investigations such as soil properties and the presence of groundwater. Thus, as long as the site isn't clearly identified, uncertainties remain regarding those aspects leading to questions regarding the feasibility of the project. However, it is still possible to pursue the opportunity investigations with multiple options still available, the consequence will be either to work with conservative assumptions, which may lead to overdesign, or to spend more time and money on site investigations (groundwater / soil properties).

¹³ AixWeather. <https://ebc-tools.eonerc.rwth-aachen.de/en/aixweather>

¹⁴ Meteonorm Software. Meteotest AG. <https://mn8.meteonorm.com/>

¹⁵ Documentation Meteonorm Climate API. <https://docs.meteonorm.com/docs/getting-started>

Sources

Free to use sources:

- First, fast worldwide screening can be done with the help of satellite images accessible via e.g. Google Maps¹⁶ or Google earth¹⁷. However, users should be aware that the data might not always be up to date, especially in remote areas, and the resolution may vary depending on the location.
- In Austria, specific information for specific property such as land register number and general classification regarding land dedication (in German, Flächenwidmung) e.g. general residential area, industrial area, etc. can be obtained from web-GIS systems of each regional state, e.g. Digitaler Atlas¹⁸ in Styria. Notice that specifics about the suitability of the land will be determined by local, federal and national legislation (e.g. federal spatial planning act, land dedication plan, Environmental protection laws). The same is true for Germany, where web-GIS system for individual states are available for free, such as <https://thuringenviewer.thueringen.de/thviewer/> or <https://www.geoportal.hessen.de/>.
- In Denmark, www.plandata.dk is a digital register for land use planning. The purpose of Plandata.dk is to ensure easy access to public plans for local, municipal and regional planning. Anyone can search for local plans and other types of plans in the map module, and municipalities can report plans. The selected content is transferable to the QGIS program to work with it.
- In France, www.geoportail.gouv.fr provide public information on the use of the land, the environmental protections, natural and industrial risk planning. Information about urban planning is available at www.geoportail-urbanisme.gouv.fr.

Cost-based sources:

- Some specific partners can provide cost-based tool which gather all the dataset relevant for the screening of the land, including the owner of the land (if it is public or owned by a society): E.g. horizon-sogefi (<https://www.sogefi-sig.com/horizon/>), promolead (<https://www.promolead.fr/>), kelfoncier (<https://kelfoncier.com/>).
- Contact with local real estate agencies.

3.3 Presence of groundwater and water level

Relevance

The presence of groundwater is a key aspect for any LTES integration concept.

On the technical side, groundwater directly impacts heat losses during operation, affecting the system's efficiency. Assessing the depth of groundwater presence is crucial for accurately evaluating the expected

¹⁶ Google Maps. <https://www.google.at/maps/preview>

¹⁷ Google Earth. <https://earth.google.com/web/>

¹⁸ Digital Atlas Steiermark. Land Steiermark. <https://gis.stmk.gv.at/>

thermal performance of the LTES and evaluating the need to consider measures to mitigate heat losses (e.g. insulation or thermal barriers).

On the environmental side, the presence of groundwater necessitates a careful assessment of the LTES's effects on the groundwater. Water bodies are highly protected in many countries and are not allowed to be heated up beyond a certain temperature, so the presence of groundwater will require consultations with various authorities to determine applicable regulations for the project.

On the economic side, handling groundwater can be costly. Pumping groundwater away before excavation is possible, but it can sometimes lead to soil issues (e.g. if the soil is sandy). In some cases, a permanent groundwater removal solution should be used (such as a cut-off wall or drains), which is also costly.

Overall, groundwater presents challenges from both technical, economic and environmental-legal perspectives. It can significantly influence the design and potentially jeopardize the project's success at a given location. Therefore, this data should be collected early in the project phase and is essential for the location selection process.

Sources

Free to use sources:

- In Austria,
 - database on measurements at national level provided by the federal ministry of agriculture, forestry, regions and water management (<https://www.ehyd.gv.at/>). Averaged monthly values and yearly maxima and minima for groundwater level (indicated in meters above Adriatic) are available for many measurement stations, in some cases monthly values for groundwater are also available. For convenience, data can be also downloaded as report (Hydrographisches Jahrbuch) <https://wasser.umweltbundesamt.at/hydjb/search/search.xhtml>.
 - databases provided via web-GIS systems of each regional state. E.g. DORIS in upper Austria, Umweltgut in Vienna, SAGIS in Salzburg, Niederösterreich Atlas in lower Austria, etc. Notice that the quality and coverage of the data of the different for the databases differ from one another.
- In Denmark, GEUS' Jupiter-database developed a tool to screen potential of upper subsurface for PTES relevant hydrogeological and geological conditions, but also for other technologies such as Borehole TES and Aquifer TES.
- In France, data on existing structures (drillings, boreholes, wells and springs) are available on the site of Bureau d'Etude Géologiques et Minières (BRGM).
- In Germany, geological information on national level is available from the Geothermal Information System GeotIS (www.geotis.de) and from the Federal Institute for Geosciences and Natural

Resources (www.bgr.bund.de). In addition, most states have their own geological services with sometimes additional and more detailed information. E.g. the BGR together with the respective land geological services (<https://www.infogeo.de/>) is sharing results of borehole drillings free of charge on the website¹⁹.

Cost-based sources:

- Local investigation of the soil carried out by a geotechnical expert (see relevance description for dataset on “soil properties”).

3.4 Soil properties

Relevance

Soil properties are essential for the feasibility of a PTES project and should be investigated early in a feasibility study for a PTES (right after the opportunity phase is finished, and the potential of the LTES solution is known) to prevent any unexpected issues that could critically impact its development.

The geotechnical study of the ground of a given location can determine if the soil is suitable for the construction of a PTES: excavation, building of the embankments, slope of the PTES, stability of the construction, etc. In addition to those factors, the thermal properties of the soil can help determine with more precision the expected thermal losses of a PTES. Additionally, the mechanical behavior of the soil during and after the use phase can be estimated, as a cyclic of permanent temperature change might lead to heaving or settlements in consolidated soils and in some soils, loss in strength. The temperature aspects are usually not included in traditional site investigations and may require special knowledge and/or laboratory equipment.

A geotechnical investigation shall address the following:

- Geological survey: Assessment of the types of soil and their variations within the area.
- Groundwater analysis: Determination of groundwater levels and their fluctuations due to seasonal changes and precipitation.
- Geotechnical soil parameters: Measurement and estimation of key soil parameters, including classification, strength, deformation, permeability and compactability (re-use of soil in embankments).
- Thermal soil properties: Measurements of thermal conductivity etc.

¹⁹ Borehole location map Germany:

<https://boreholemap.bgr.de/mapapps/resources/apps/boreholemap/index.html?lang=de>

A site investigation involves fieldwork, typically including boreholes with soil sampling and in-situ tests. The number and depth of the investigation points are specified by Eurocode 7 part 2²⁰, but obviously depend on the actual soil and project in general. Laboratory work follows fieldwork. This investigation is carried out usually during the feasibility study, after the opportunity phase showed the potential of the LTES solution.

The investigations will typically be performed in steps:

- Preliminary investigations (supplementing desk studies for evaluation of suitability of specific site)
- Design investigations (for extracting soil and groundwater parameters)
- Optimization investigations (to handle specific issues, e.g. temperature effects on soil parameters)
- Supervision and necessary monitoring (during and after establishment)

It is recommended to involve geotechnical expertise at the beginning of a project.

Sources

Free to use sources:

- Databases provided via web-GIS systems.
 - In Austria, the Austrian soil map²¹ provides soil information for 2.86 million hectares of agricultural land. Each zone (mapping unit) is associated to a representative (reference) soil profile which is described in detail including information such as texture, humus and lime content, and pH value to a depth of 1 m.
 - In France, geology maps are available on the site²² of Bureau d'Etude Géologiques et Minières (BRGM).
 - In Germany, geological information on national level is available from the Geothermal Information System GeotIS (www.geotis.de) and from the Federal Institute for Geosciences and Natural Resources (www.bgr.bund.de). In addition, most states have their own geological services with sometimes additional and more detailed information. E.g. the BGR together with the respective land geological services (<https://www.infogeo.de/>) is sharing results of borehole drillings free of charge on the website²³.
 - The European Commission has a collection of national maps and datasets, mostly according to the FAO-standard, on their site under the portal of the European Soil Data Centre (ESDAC): <https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/>

²⁰ EN 1997-2 (2007): Eurocode 7: Geotechnical design - Part 2: Ground investigation and testing [Authority: The European Union Per Regulation 305/2011, Directive 98/34/EC, Directive 2004/18/EC].

²¹ Österreichische Bodenkarte am BFW. <https://bodenkarte.at/>.

²² Cartes géologiques. Bureau d'Etude Géologiques et Minières. <https://infoterre.brgm.fr/page/cartes-geologiques>

²³ Borehole location map Germany:

<https://boreholemap.bgr.de/mapapps/resources/apps/boreholemap/index.html?lang=de>

Cost-based sources:

- Local investigation of the soil carried out by a geotechnical expert.

3.5 Cost data: CAPEX and OPEX of the different heating technologies

Relevance

Energy system concepts require both technical analysis and economic assessment. Economic key performance indicators (KPIs), such as heat price in EUR/MWh and overall investment costs, significantly influence the choice between different energy system concepts. Consequently, cost data is crucial during the early project phases when various energy system concepts are developed, evaluated, and compared, providing a solid foundation for decision-makers. This cost information also remains relevant in later stages, including the construction and operation phases.

A common approach to energy system concept design is to have an iterative process. The energy system concepts and information at the early phase of a project are not concrete enough to justify starting inquiries with different engineering offices or manufacturers to obtain actual and accurate cost data to carry out the economic assessment. In this regard, the use of general unit cost data finds its place. Due to its simplicity, it provides valuable information without the need of detailed design information. These sources are typically based on industry benchmarks, historical data, or standardized costs from similar projects.

Sources

Beside any in-house experience from e.g. previous projects, literature is a good source of information. The following sources are classified by technology. NB: The references might have been published in different years and can be based or refer to specific set of countries, potentially causing different values to be too inaccurate or out-dated due to site specific reasons, technology development or inflation. Therefore, one should proceed with caution and adapt the values as one sees fit.

Free to use sources:

The document “Long term (2050) projections of techno-economic performance of large-scale heating and cooling in the EU”²⁴ provides financial information (investment, operation, and maintenance) for a wide range of heating technologies. Furthermore, it also provides information on a typical cost distribution in % of

²⁴ Carlsson, J. et al. 2017. Long term (2050) projections of techno-economic performance of large-scale heating and cooling in the EU. <https://dx.doi.org/10.2760/24422>.

a project (cost for main equipment, balance of plant, etc.). Similar economic (and also environmental data such as CO₂ emission factors) can be found in the “technical catalogue” for Germany²⁵ and Denmark²⁶.

Besides the above technology overarching reference, some technology specific references are listed below,

- Solar thermal: Different sources are available for this technology, among them the deliverables from IEA SHC, specifically Task 52²⁷ (Subtask B and C) and Task 55²⁸. Furthermore, default values from feasibility tools can be used as reference, a list of solar thermal installation related tools can be found in the SDH web page²⁹.
- TES: Similarly to the solar thermal installations, default values from previous projects such as SUNSTORE 3, SUNSTORE 4 or Flex-TES³⁰ can be used as reference. Furthermore, data from existing projects and derived correlations can be found in several sources, e.g. deliverable 2.3³¹ of the Flexynets European project. The technology catalogue about energy storage from the Danish Energy Agency also contains a chapter about seasonal TES and is available for free, with techno-economic data from Danish projects.
- Heat pumps: Cost data for different types of reports from IEA TCP program on heat pumps, e.g. Annex 48³² or Annex 58³³.
- In general, the work from various IEA TCP (Energy Storage, Solar Heating and Cooling, Heat Pump Technology, etc.) projects (called “task” or “annex”) contain deliverables and references with relevant techno-economic data for different components and technologies.

Additionally to the investment and O&M related costs for different technologies, price for fuel sources (e.g. electricity, gas and biomass) are relevant to evaluate the different technical concepts. The DH operator will most likely not be able to provide detailed cost information because this information is treated as sensitive and kept confidential. However, the DH operator should be able to provide some guiding values to work with. Additionally, to any information given by the DH operator, one can obtain information on fuel costs from the following data sources,

²⁵ KEA Klimaschutz- und Energieagentur Baden-Württemberg GmbH. <https://www.kea-bw.de/waermewende/angebote/downloads>.

²⁶ Danish Energy Agency. <https://ens.dk/en/analyses-and-statistics/technology-catalogues>.

²⁷ Solar Heat and Energy Economics in Urban Environments. IEA SHC Task 52. <https://task52.iea-shc.org/>.

²⁸ Integrating Large SHC Systems into DHC Networks. IEA SHC Task 55. <https://task55.iea-shc.org/>.

²⁹ SDH calculation tools. <https://www.solar-district-heating.eu/en/tools/>.

³⁰ https://planenergi.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/01/FLEX_TES-Implementationreport_final_23.12.23.pdf

³¹ Sveinbjörnsson, D., et al. D2.3 – Large Storage Systems for DHC Networks. 2017.

³² Rieberer, R., et al. Industrial Heat Pumps, Second Phase. IEA Heat Pump Technology (HPT) Programme Annex 48. Task 4: Training materials for industrial heat pumps. August 2019.

³³ Benjamin, Z. et al. High-Temperature Heat Pumps. Task 1 – Technologies. IEA Heat Pump Technology (HPT) Programme Annex 58. Report no. HPT-AN58-2. August 2023.

- Data on electricity and gas price can be retrieved from official information sources such as EUROSTAT³⁴ or via the data and analysis section of the European Commission³⁵. Alternative data sources are Ember³⁶ (include hourly, daily, and monthly electricity price data), Bruegel³⁷ (includes different dashboards on electricity price), and Energy-Charts³⁸ (hourly electricity price data or several European and EU-member countries) or AWATTar³⁹ (Company that provides consumers with real-time pricing in Austria. Datasets on hourly price from 2019 onwards can be downloaded in .csv or .xlsx format).
- Data on biomass price is a more local information that should be obtained from rather regional or national data sources. E.g. for Austria, the publications from the Carinthian Chamber of Agriculture⁴⁰ at regional level, and datasets from Statistik Austria⁴¹ at national level.
- For Denmark, historical data on electricity and gas prices are provided by Energinet (see for instance <https://en.energinet.dk/Gas/Tariffs-and-Fees/Historical-tariff-data/>, or their open energy data service available online: <https://www.energidataservice.dk/>), as well as some predictions.

Cost-based sources:

- Different companies (e.g. S&P Global⁴² and Ricardo⁴³) do provide long-term forecast for electricity price as well as market and risk analysis for different storage and production technologies for the heating and power sector.
- The tool energyTRADE (from the Danish company EMD international, see <https://www.emd-international.com/energytrade/>) is a software solution, mostly used for optimisation of cogeneration plants operation, which gives access to electricity spot price prognosis, based on various input data such as weather forecasts, expected heat demand, state of charge of a TES, etc.

³⁴ Electricity prices components for non-household consumers - annual data (from 2007 onwards) EUROSTAT.

https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/nrg_pc_205_c/default/table?lang=en&category=nrg.nrg_price.nrg_pc.

³⁵ Data and analysis. European Commission. https://energy.ec.europa.eu/data-and-analysis_en.

³⁶ European wholesale electricity price data. Ember. <https://ember-climate.org/data-catalogue/european-wholesale-electricity-price-data/>.

³⁷ Electricity tariffs dashboard. Bruegel. <https://www.bruegel.org/dataset/electricity-tariffs-dashboard>.

³⁸ https://www.energy-charts.info/charts/price_spot_market/chart.htm?l=en&c=EU.

³⁹ aWATTar. <https://www.awattar.at/>.

⁴⁰ Carinthian Chamber of Agriculture. <https://ktn.lko.at/startseite+2400+++1078>.

⁴¹ STATCube. Statistik Austria.

<https://statcube.at/statistik.at/ext/statcube/jsf/dataCatalogueExplorer.xhtml>.

⁴² Platts Global Integrated Energy Model. S&P Global.

<https://www.spglobal.com/commodityinsights/en/products-services/energy-transition/global-integrated-energy-model>

⁴³ Energy decarbonisation. Ricardo. <https://www.ricardo.com/en/solutions/energy-decarbonisation>

3.6 Load and temperature profiles of the DH-system

Relevance

To be mentioned is that the load profile and operating temperatures will highly influence the design and operation of the LTES system and should be therefore be addressed in this document. Load profiles are a key information needed for the design and operation of a DH system. The viability of a DH project relies heavily on this information, which is used to calculate KPIs for heat demand density (heat demand per meter of trench or area).

Additionally, understanding the load profile allows for an estimation of consumption patterns throughout the year (base and peak loads), providing essential insights for defining the optimal mix of heating technologies. The load profile becomes even more critical when integrating technologies that may produce surplus heat (e.g. non-dispatchable heating technologies such as solar thermal and/or dispatchable ones that are not heat-driven e.g. capitalize on electricity market) and the integration of (L)TES is being considered.

Furthermore, the heat demand has an influence on the operational temperatures of a traditional district heating system. Supply temperatures are increased in periods of high demand (cold weather) and reduced or kept constant at a lower level for summer periods with reduced demand.

Sources

In regards of the data sources, two main scenarios should be distinguished. The case where the district heating system exists and the case where the DH system does not exist yet and should be built (with or without existing consumers/buildings).

Existing DH-system:

In case the DH-system exists, one can expect the DH operator to have historic data on the heat generation and consumption side. Data at the heat generation side can be often provided at the desired quality (e.g. hourly values) without restrictions. However, at the consumer side, the data can often not be provided either due to legal issues (use is restricted and/or cannot be provided to third parties without authorization) or simply the data is not being stored with the desired resolution because data at consumer side is merely being used for billing purposes rather than system optimization. This information is basic for the understanding of the system and the definition and modelling of the energy system concepts.

As highlighted above in section 3.1 Weather data, the data used for system analyses and simulation studies must be consistent. Therefore, it is recommended to provide and utilize the load profile together with the corresponding weather data. In the analysis is conducted under different conditions, such as a typical year (e.g. based on Test Reference Year weather data) or extreme years, the original load profile should not be used directly. Instead, it is advisable to derive and apply a correlation between the load profile and relevant variables, such as outdoor air temperature or other meaningful factors (e.g. time of the day/year).

If clear datasets are unavailable, they must be obtained, which is often a time-consuming process. Notice that knowing the heat load based on data from heat production units is normally good enough since the amount of heat that needs to be supplied to the DHN is usually sufficient information (the heat amount that is used to supply the heat consumers and the share attributed to the heat losses usually don't need to be distinguished). This lack of clarity can be tolerated when no strong changes on how the system is operated are done (e.g. heat is mostly provided at same temperature levels and from the same locations). If this is not the case, and the hydraulics of the DH-system do change and become a topic of the analysis, a better characterization of the heat demand and temperatures (rather mass flow rates) might be necessary to analyse the technical concept.

Non existing DH-system:

In case the district heating does not exist, the heat load profile can only be estimated (or generated) based on information from the consumer side.

In regard of the temperature profiles, this is in this case part of the design problem and cannot be estimated or calculated, instead the DH system should be analysed to be able to define "optimal" supply temperatures and estimate the return temperatures. Thus, the estimation of the supply and return temperature profile is part of a techno-economic optimization problem and out of scope of this document.

The accurate estimation of the heat demand can be a time-consuming task; therefore, it makes sense that the effort put into the estimation is limited and proportional to the relevance of the consumers. Here it is important to remark that the overall heat demand of each consumer is composed of heat demand for heating purposes, hot water preparation and for special cases such as industrial consumers, process heat. In Annex A: Determination of load profile, several approaches to estimate the heat demand for space heating and reference values for domestic hot water demand are presented.

Annex A: Determination of load profile

The following annex describes different ways on how the load profile for heating purposes can be generated or estimated as well as some guide values in regard of domestic hot water consumption.

A.1 Heating demand

- **Direct contact with the main consumers.**

The main consumers are key to the implementation of a district heating system. Asking for their interest and specific heat needs is a “must” and should be done to ensure the definition of a proper design and operation strategy and thus have a viable project.

- **Estimation of heat demand based on expert knowledge and experience values.**

First approximate heating demands can be based on experience values, e.g. from planning handbooks such as QM Holzheizwerke⁴⁴ (see chapter 11.2, especially table 11.1).

- **Estimation of the yearly heating demand using the Heating Degree Day (HDD) method.**

The HDD provides a simple method to estimate when a building requires heating and with some assumptions the yearly heat demand. The HDD method assumes that if the daily average outdoor air temperature goes below a certain threshold value T_{th} (to be defined), there is heating demand.

The HDD is usually calculated as the sum of the difference between the daily average outdoor air temperature $T_{m,i}$ and a reference temperature T_{ref} , see equations (1) and (2). The daily average can be calculated from the hourly temperatures. Further methods to calculate Degree Days can be found in Mourshed, M.⁴⁵.

$$HDD = \sum_{i=1}^{n=365} \Delta T^i \quad (1)$$

$$\Delta T_i = \begin{cases} T_{ref} - T_{m,i} & \text{for } T_{m,i} \leq T_{th} \\ 0 & \text{for } T_{m,i} > T_{th} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

The HDD can be calculated using local weather data and setting the reference (T_{ref}) and threshold (T_{th}) temperature as one sees fit. For a first approximation the HDD values from Eurostat can be used. Monthly values of the HDD have been calculated using $T_{ref}=18$ °C and $T_{th}=15$ °C at national

⁴⁴ QM Holzheiwerte Band 4. Planungshandbuch. (2002) ISBN 978-3-937441-96-2.

⁴⁵ Mourshed, M. (2012). Relationship between annual mean temperature and degree-days. Energy and Buildings, 54, 418–425. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2012.07.024>.

level. A subset of yearly and monthly HDD values for several target countries are summarized in Table 4.

Table 4: HDD in K for every month of several EU countries for 2018. Data retrieved from Eurostat database⁴⁶. HDD Calculated for $T_{ref} = 18\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $T_{th} = 15\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$.

Country	Month											
	Dec	Nov	Oct	Sep	Aug	Jul	Jun	May	Apr	Mar	Feb	Jan
Austria	543	392	219	88	24	20	47	88	164	504	593	515
Germany	433	371	200	73	11	3	22	63	150	470	543	435
Italy	344	188	57	16	5	4	10	39	97	298	371	325
Poland	513	400	225	71	6	10	29	53	144	548	594	531
Slovenia	506	316	147	51	7	0	6	27	106	443	530	444

Known the heating degree days (HDD), the yearly heating demand in MWh/a can be calculated with two different approaches,

- **Use of an overall heat loss coefficient**

As described in Kalogirou S.⁴⁷ the heating demand D_h in kJ can be obtained with help of equation (3). Notice that the method can be adapted to calculate e.g. daily or monthly demand by using daily or monthly values of HDD respectively.

The overall heat loss coefficient UA in kW/K mainly represents the air infiltration and heat transmission losses through the building envelope. It should be noted then that this method does not include internal heat gains and dynamics characteristics of the building, e.g. heat capacities, are disregarded.

$$D_h = \frac{86400\text{ s}}{1\text{ day}} \cdot UA \cdot HDD \quad (3)$$

The UA value needs to be defined. It can be estimated based on the construction data, done after knowing the envelope geometry and construction materials, or as shown in Kalogirou S.⁴⁷ derived from design values of the heating system. E.g. based on the installed heating capacity

⁴⁶ Cooling and heating degree days by country - monthly data. EUROSTAT.

https://doi.org/10.2908/NRG_CHDD_M.

⁴⁷ Kalogirou, S. (2014). Solar Space Heating and Cooling. In Solar Energy Engineering (pp. 323–395).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-397270-5.00006-6>.

Q_{inst} in kW. In this regard, it can be assumed that the heating system have been sized for specific indoor and outdoor air temperatures (T_{indoor} and $T_{outdoor}$ respectively) according to equation (4).

$$UA = \frac{Q_{inst}}{(T_{indoor} - T_{outdoor})} \quad (4)$$

- **Extrapolation of heat demand**

HDD can be used to normalize the heat consumption of a building as shown in Equation (5).

$$Heating\ demand_{normalized} = \frac{Heating\ demand}{HDD} \quad (5)$$

The normalized heat consumption as defined in Equation (5) is usually used for a fair comparison of the energy consumption between buildings in different regions. Nevertheless, the normalized heat demand can be also used with help of Equation (6) to extrapolate the heat demand of the chosen building (or group of buildings) to another climate, i.e another location. This method can be useful when no information regarding the heat consumption of the buildings in the region is available, but the heat demand is known for some other region with a similar building stock. The known heat demand of similar buildings of other regions can be normalized and extrapolated to the new location under consideration to have a rough estimate on the expected heating demand.

$$Heating\ demand_{new\ loc.} = HDD_{new\ loc.} \cdot Heating\ demand_{normalized} \quad (6)$$

A.2 Domestic hot water (DHW) demand

In regard of the heat demand for domestic hot water production (DHW), several sources can be mentioned. Based on over 2 Mio. accounting measured data, online-questionnaire, literature research and data from a specialized software co2online, the heat demand for how water preparation could be accurately estimated in the project “Nutzenergiebedarf für Warmwasser in Wohngebäuden”⁴⁸. Based on data from the Techem and Brunata companies, hot water energy demand per usable area is between 9 and 13 kWh/(a.m²) for multifamily houses. Based on data from the company ista, the average for water demand is 11,1 kWh/(a.m²) and specifically for multifamily houses they report 10 kWh/(a.m²). Based on 331 data sets for single family

⁴⁸ Offermann, M., Manteufel, von, B., Hermelink, A., John, A., Ahrens, C., Jahnke, K., & Zastra, K. (2017). Nutzenergiebedarf für Warmwasser in Wohngebäuden. Bonn. Retrieved from <https://www.bbsr.bund.de/BBSR/DE/veroeffentlichungen/bbsr-online/2017/bbsr-online-17-2017.html>.

houses collected by means of an online survey, the average of heat demand for DHW was calculated to 9,2 kWh/(a.m²).

Based on the mean values from the data analysed, Offermann et al.⁴⁸ proposes to use Equation (7) to estimate the heat demand for domestic hot water per usable floor area E_{DHW} in kWh/(a.m²). Where \tilde{A} , is the median of useful floor area of residential units of the buildings.

$$E_{DHW} = (15 - (\tilde{A} \cdot 0,04)) \quad (7)$$

A minimum limit for the heat demand for domestic hot water is set to 7 kWh/(a.m²). Thus the obtained values with Equation (7) are between 7 and 15 kWh/(a.m²). Similar to the ones used in the TABULA WebTool⁴⁹, 10 kWh/(a.m²) for single family houses and terraced houses and 15 kWh/(a.m²) for multifamily houses and apartment blocks, but lower than 20 kWh/(a.m²), the value suggested in Good et al.⁵⁰.

A.3 GIS-based tools

Finally, it is worth mentioning that there are some freely available GIS-tools that can be used to obtain a rough estimation on heat demand and can be used together with the HDD to estimate the heat demand. These are e.g. the Pan-European Thermal Atlas 4, THERMOS and HOTMAPS.

- **Pan-European Thermal Atlas 4**

The Pan-European Thermal Atlas 4⁵¹ (Peta4) is an online map carried out within the Heat Roadmap Europe 4 (HRE4) of which the main aim is the mapping of relevant information for the heat and cold market. It includes information about heating and cooling demands as well as potential of excess and renewable heat sources. A broad description regarding the methodology, assumptions, data, and tools used is given in Persson, Möller, and Wiechers⁵².

Heating demand densities are available by hectare grid resolution for 14 EU member states, among them Italy, Poland, Germany and Austria. Specific values of the cell values cannot be read, results are presented in four intervals, specifically: < 50 TJ/km², 50 – 120 TJ/km², 120 – 300 TJ/km² and > 300 TJ/km². Notice that 1 TJ/km² are approximately 277,8 kWh/m². A summary of the key features, a brief description of the information available in PETA4 and example of its potential applicability, i.e. use cases, can be found in Persson, Möller, Wiechers, and Rothballer⁵³.

⁴⁹ TABULA WebTool. (n.d.). Retrieved 1 August 2019, from <http://webtool.building-typology.eu/#sd>.

⁵⁰ Good, J., Biedermann, F., Bühler, R., Bunk, H., Rudolf Gabathuler, H., Hammerschmid, A., Rakos, C. (2008). QM-Planungshandbuch. (C. A. R. M. E. N. e. V. Straubing, Ed.) (2nd ed.).

⁵¹ Pan-European Thermal Atlas 4.3. (n.d.). Retrieved 1 August 2019, from <https://heatroadmap.eu/peta4/>

⁵² Persson, U., Möller, B., and Wiechers, E. (2015). Methodologies and assumptions used in the mapping (D2.3).

⁵³ Persson, U., Möller, B., Wiechers, E., and Rothballer, C. (2015). Maps Manual for Lead-Users (D2.4).

- **THERMOS**

During the THERMOS⁵⁴ project, a free, open-source software has been developed that aims to offer local authorities address-level data for the optimal design of new or expansions of a district heating systems. Though the main application is the predesign of the district heating system and not the estimation of the heat demand, the software includes data regarding the heat demand at a building level which can be used to identify high density areas. The heat demand data is based on some/all of the following information: three-dimensional building shape/size, internal building temperatures and outdoor air temperature, building thermal efficiency and other benchmark models (e.g. water heating demand).

- **HOTMAPS**

The main goal of the HOTMAPS project is the development of an open-source heating/cooling mapping and planning toolbox and to provide default data for EU28 at national and local level. The HOTMAPS toolbox⁵⁵ is already available and contains data at different scales resolution, being 1 hectare the finest grid element and national the coarsest. More detailed information can be found at their website and the toolbox wiki⁵⁶.

Additionally, to the above-mentioned GIS tools, there are two relevant EU projects, TABULA⁵⁷ and its follow-up project EPISCOPE⁵⁸, from which data for the specific heat consumption of different building classes can be obtained. During these projects residential building topologies have been developed for 13 European countries. Each national typology consists of a classification scheme grouping buildings according to their size, age and further parameters and a set of exemplary buildings representing the building types. Following the seasonal method described in EN ISO 13790 the energy need for space heating and domestic hot water preparation has been calculated for each of this building topology, see Loga and Diefenach⁵⁹ for more information about the method. Due to the lack of information about the real utilisation conditions and exact thermal properties of existing buildings, deviations between the obtained results with the model and measured consumption can be expected. Because of this uncertainty, the obtained results are complemented with a second type of calculation, it mainly consists in the application of an empirical adaption factor to the obtained results. Nevertheless, the TABULA project can serve together with the information of the land

⁵⁴ THERMOS project. <https://www.thermos-project.eu/home/>.

⁵⁵ Hotmaps toolbox. (n.d.). Retrieved 5 August 2024, from <https://www.hotmaps.hevs.ch/map>.

⁵⁶ Hotmaps toolbox. (n.d.). Retrieved 5 August 2024, from <https://wiki.hotmaps.eu/en/Home>.

⁵⁷ IEE Project TABULA. (n.d.). Retrieved 24 July 2019, from <http://episcope.eu/iee-project/tabula/>.

⁵⁸ EE Project EPISCOPE. (n.d.). Retrieved 24 July 2019, from <http://episcope.eu/iee-project/episcope/>.

⁵⁹ Loga, T., & Diefenach, N. (2013). TABULA Calculation Method - Energy Use for Heating and Domestic Hot Water -. Institut Wohnen und Umwelt GmbH.

registry to characterise the energy consumption of specific area. Values for the specific heat demand can be obtained directly from the webtool or using the freely available (on demand) excel workbook “TABULA.xls”.

